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Research Article

**DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF AN HPLC METHOD
FOR DETECTION AND QUANTIFICATION OF
MIDOSTAURIN IN BULK AND MARKETED
PHARMACEUTICAL DOSAGE FORM****CH .Kantlam¹, CH.Suchitra^{2*}, Dhara Shivanand³, Farha Maheen³, G.Veena³, K.
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Hayathnagar, Rangareddy, Telangana**Abstract:**

A simple, rapid, specific and accurate reverse phase high performance liquid chromatographic method has been developed for the validated of Midostaurin in bulk as well as in marketed pharmaceutical dosage form. This separation was performed on a Symmetry ODS (C18) RP Column, 250 mm x 4.6 mm, 5µm column with Acetonitrile, Methanol and 0.1% OPA in the ratio of 60:30:10 as mobile phase at a flow rate of 1.0 mL min⁻¹ with UV detection at 235 nm; the constant column temperature was Ambient. The run time under these chromatographic conditions was less than 6.0 min. The retention time of Midostaurin was found to be 2.570min. The calibration plot was linear over the concentration range of 6–14 µg mL⁻¹ with limits of detection and quantification values of 0.8 and 0.24ng mL⁻¹ respectively. The mean % assay of marketed formulation was found to be 99.79%, and % recovery was observed in the range of 98-102%. Relative standard deviation for the precision study was found <2%.The developed method is simple, precise, specific, accurate and rapid, making it suitable for estimation of Midostaurin in bulk and marketed pharmaceutical dosage form dosage form.

Keywords: Midostaurin, RP-HPLC, Validation, Accuracy, Precision, Robustness, ICH Guidelines.

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INTRODUCTION:

Midostaurin is an organic heteroocyclic compound that is the N-benzoyl derivative of staurosporine. It has a role as an EC 2.7.11.13 (protein kinase C) inhibitor and an antineoplastic agent [1]. It is an indolocarbazole, an organic heteroocyclic compound, a member of benzamides and a gamma-lactam. It is functionally related to a staurosporine. Midostaurin (as Rydapt) is a multitarget kinase inhibitor for the treatment for adult patients with newly diagnosed acute myeloid leukemia (AML) who have a specific genetic mutation called FLT3. It was initially characterized as a potential broad-spectrum

antineoplastic agent, with activity toward diverse solid and hematopoietic tumors [2]. It was approved on April 28, 2017 and has shown to increase the overall survival rate in patients with AML as an adjunct therapy along with chemotherapeutic agents. Midostaurin is a Kinase Inhibitor. The mechanism of action of Midostaurin is as a Receptor Tyrosine Kinase Inhibitor [3]. The IUPAC Name and Chemical Structure of Midostaurin is N-[(2S, 3R, 4R, 6R)-3-methoxy-2-methyl-16-oxo-29-oxa-1, 7, 17-triazaoctacyclo [12.12.2.12, 6.07, 28.08, 13.015, 19.020, 27.021, 26] nonacosa-8, 10, 12, 14, 19, 21, 23, 25, 27-nonaen-4-yl]-N-methyl benzamide

Fig-1: Chemical Structure of Midostaurin

MATERIALS AND METHODS**Instruments Used:**

Table-1: List of Instrument Used

S. No.	Instruments/Equipments/Apparatus
1.	HPLC with Empower2 Software with Isocratic with UV-Visible Detector (Waters).
2.	T60-LAB INDIA UV – Vis spectrophotometer
3.	Electronic Balance (SHIMADZU ATY224)
4.	Ultra Sonicator (Wensar wuc-2L)
5.	Thermal Oven
6.	Symmetry ODS RP C ₁₈ , 5μm, 15mm x 4.6mm i.d.
7.	P ^H Analyzer (ELICO)
8.	Vacuum filtration kit (BOROSIL)

Chemicals / Reagents Used:

Table-2: List of Chemicals used

S.No.	Name	Specifications		Manufacturer/Supplier
		Purity	Grade	
1.	Doubled distilled water	99.9%	HPLC	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai
2.	Methanol	99.9%	HPLC	Loba Chem; Mumbai.
3.	Dipotassium orthophosphate hydrogen	96%	A.R.	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai
4.	Acetonitrile	99.9%	HPLC	Loba Chem; Mumbai.
5.	Potassium dihydrogen orthophosphate	99.9%	A.R.	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai
6.	Sodium hydroxide	99.9%	A.R.	Sd fine-Chem ltd; Mumbai
7.	Hydrochloric acid	99.9%	A.R.	Loba Chem; Mumbai.
8.	Hydrogen Peroxide	99.9%	A.R.	Loba Chem; Mumbai.

Method Development by HPLC:**Selection of Wavelength:**

The Standard & Sample Stock Solutions were prepared separately by dissolving standard & sample in a solvent in mobile phase diluting with the same solvent. (After optimization of all conditions) for UV analysis. It scanned in the UV spectrum in the range of 200 to 400nm. This has been performed to know the maxima of Midostaurin, so that the same wave number can be utilized in HPLC UV detector for estimating the Midostaurin [4]. The scanned UV spectrum is attached in the following page,

Sample & Standard Preparation for the UV-Spectrophotometer Analysis

25 mg of Midostaurin standard was transferred into 25 ml volumetric flask, dissolved & make up to volume with mobile phase. Further dilution was done by transferring 0.5 ml of the above solution into a 10ml volumetric flask and make up to volume with mobile phase [5].

Optimization of Chromatographic Conditions: The chromatographic conditions were optimized by different means. (Using different column, different mobile phase, different flow rate, different detection wavelength & different diluents for sample preparation etc.

Table-3: Summary of Process Optimization

Column Used	Mobile Phase	Flow Rate	Wave length	Observation	Result
Symmetry C ₁₈ , ODS, Reverse Phase, 250 mm x 4.6 mm, 5µm, Column.	Methanol : Acetonitrile = 40 : 60	1.0ml/min	235nm	Very Low response	Method rejected
Symmetry C ₁₈ , ODS, Reverse Phase, 250 mm x 4.6 mm, 5µm, Column.	Methanol : Acetonitrile = 55 : 45	1.0ml/min	235nm	Low response	Method rejected
Symmetry C ₁₈ , ODS, Reverse Phase, 250 mm x 4.6 mm, 5µm, Column.	Acetonitrile : Water = 50:50	1.0ml/min	235nm	Tailing peaks	Method rejected
Symmetry C ₁₈ , ODS, Reverse Phase, 250 mm x 4.6 mm, 5µm, Column.	Methanol : Water = 70:30	1.0ml/min	235nm	Resolution was not good	Method rejected
Symmetry C ₁₈ , ODS, Reverse Phase, 250 mm x 4.6 mm, 5µm, Column.	ACN : Methanol: 0.1% OPA = 70:25:5	1.0ml/min	235nm	Tailing peak	Method rejected
Symmetry C ₁₈ , ODS, Reverse Phase, 250 mm x 4.6 mm, 5µm, Column.	ACN : Methanol: 0.1% OPA = 60:30:10	1.0ml/min	235nm	Nice peak	Method accepted

Preparation of Mobile Phase:

600ml of HPLC Grade Acetonitrile, 300ml of HPLC Grade Methanol and 100ml 0.1% OPA were mixed well and degassed in ultrasonic water bath for 15 minutes. The solution was filtered through 0.45 µm filter under vacuum filtration [6].

Method Validation

Method validation is the process used to confirm that the analytical procedure employed for a specific test is suitable for its intended use. Results from method validation can be used to judge the quality, reliability and consistency of analytical results; it is an integral part of any good analytical practice [7-10].

System Suitability Parameters: The theory of chromatography has been used as the basis for system-suitability tests, which are set of quantitative criteria that test the suitability of the chromatographic system to identify and quantify

drug related samples by HPLC at any step of the pharmaceutical analysis [11].

1. Specificity: Specificity is the ability to assess unequivocally the analyte in the presence of components which may be expected to be present. Typically these might include impurities, degradants, matrix, etc. Lack of specificity of an individual analytical procedure may be compensated by other supporting analytical procedure(s) [12].

2. Accuracy: The accuracy of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement between the value which is accepted either as a conventional true value or an accepted reference value and the value found. This is sometimes termed trueness [13].

3. Precision: The precision of an analytical procedure expresses the closeness of agreement (degree of scatter) between a series of

measurements obtained from multiple sampling of the same homogeneous sample under the prescribed conditions. Precision may be considered at three levels: repeatability, intermediate precision and reproducibility. Precision should be investigated using homogeneous, authentic samples. However, if it is not possible to obtain a homogeneous sample it may be investigated using artificially prepared samples or a sample solution. The precision of an analytical procedure is usually expressed as the variance, standard deviation or coefficient of variation of a series of measurements [14].

3.1. Repeatability: Repeatability expresses the precision under the same operating conditions over a short interval of time. Repeatability is also termed intra-assay precision.

3.2. Intermediate precision: Intermediate precision expresses within-laboratories variations: different days, different analysts, different equipment, etc.

3.3. Reproducibility: Reproducibility expresses the precision between laboratories (collaborative studies, usually applied to standardization of methodology).

4. Detection Limit: The detection limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value [15].

5. Quantitation Limit: The quantitation limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest

amount of analyte in a sample which can be quantitatively determined with suitable precision and accuracy. The quantitation limit is a parameter of quantitative assays for low levels of compounds in sample matrices, and is used particularly for the determination of impurities and/or degradation products [16].

6. Linearity: The linearity of an analytical procedure is its ability (within a given range) to obtain test results which are directly proportional to the concentration (amount) of analyte in the sample [17].

7. Range: The range of an analytical procedure is the interval between the upper and lower concentration (amounts) of analyte in the sample (including these concentrations) for which it has been demonstrated that the analytical procedure has a suitable level of precision, accuracy and linearity [18].

8. Robustness: The robustness of an analytical procedure is a measure of its capacity to remain unaffected by small, but deliberate variations in method parameters and provides an indication of its reliability during normal usage [19].

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Analytical Method Development:

Summary of Optimized Chromatographic Conditions:

The Optimum Chromatographic conditions obtained from experiments can be summarized as below:

Table-4: Summary of Optimised Chromatographic Conditions

Mobile phase	ACN : Methanol: 0.1% OPA = 60:30:10
Column	Symmetry ODS (C ₁₈) RP Column, 250 mm x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m
Column Temperature	Ambient
Detection Wavelength	235 nm
Flow rate	1.0 ml/ min.
Run time	06 min.
Temperature of Auto sampler	Ambient
Diluent	Mobile Phase
Injection Volume	10 μ l
Type of Elution	Isocratic
Retention time	2.570 minutes

Fig-2: Chromatogram of Midostaurin in Optimized Condition

Validation of Analytical Method:

The developed chromatographic method was validated for Specificity, Linearity, Precision, Accuracy, Sensitivity, Robustness and System suitability [20].

1. Accuracy:**Recovery Study:**

To determine the accuracy of the proposed method, recovery studies were carried out by adding different amounts (80%, 100%, and 120%) of pure drug of Midostaurin were taken and 3 replications of each has been injected to HPLC system. From that percentage recovery values were calculated from the linearity equation $y = 19423x + 5444.4$ [21]. The results were shown in table-5.

Table-5: Readings of Accuracy

Conc. In ppm	Conc. Found	Peak Area	% Recovery
8	8.035	161523	100.437
8	8.153	163815	101.912
8	8.061	162023	100.762
		Avg.	101.037
		S.D	0.775
		%RSD	0.767046
Conc. In ppm	Conc. Found	Peak Area	% Recovery
10	9.930	198315	99.30
10	10.033	200320	100.33
10	10.044	200540	100.44
		Avg.	100.0233
		S.D	0.628835
		%RSD	0.628688
Conc. In ppm	Conc. Found	Peak Area	% Recovery
12	11.981	238151	99.841
12	12.066	239819	100.55
12	12.215	242712	101.791
		Avg.	100.7273
		S.D	0.987021
		%RSD	0.979894

2. Precision:**2.1. Repeatability**

The precision of each method was ascertained separately from the peak areas & retention times obtained by actual determination of six replicates of a fixed amount of drug. Midostaurin (API) [22]. The percent relative standard deviation was calculated for Midostaurin are presented in the table-6.

Table-6: Readings of Repeatability

HPLC Injection Replicates of Midostaurin	Retention Time (Minutes)	Peak Area (AUC)
Replicate – 1	2.572	197236
Replicate – 2	2.570	197762
Replicate – 3	2.573	195969
Replicate – 4	2.570	194724
Replicate – 5	2.574	198327
Replicate – 6	2.573	198711
Average		197121.5
Standard Deviation		1515.213
% RSD		0.768667

2.2. Intermediate Precision/Ruggedness:**2.2.1. Intra-Day & Inter-Day:**

The intra & inter day variation of the method was carried out & the high values of mean assay & low values of standard deviation & % RSD (% RSD < 2%) within a day & day to day variations for Midostaurin revealed that the proposed method is precise [23].

Intra Day/Day-1/Analyst-1:**Table-7: Results of Intermediate Precision Analyst 1 for Midostaurin**

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	Midostaurin	2.580	206587	3102	1.16
2	Midostaurin	2.597	206859	2986	1.18
3	Midostaurin	2.581	207854	3054	1.13
4	Midostaurin	2.573	208965	3154	1.14
5	Midostaurin	2.590	206547	3157	1.12
6	Midostaurin	2.572	209865	3268	1.18
Mean			207779.5		
Std. Dev.			1381.9336		
% RSD			0.665		

Inter Day/Day-2/Analyst-2:**Table-8: Results of Intermediate Precision Analyst 2 for Midostaurin**

S.No.	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	Midostaurin	2.580	215263	3215	1.17
2	Midostaurin	2.597	214235	3652	1.19
3	Midostaurin	2.581	213254	3496	1.15
4	Midostaurin	2.573	212367	3258	1.16
5	Midostaurin	2.590	213698	3365	1.17
6	Midostaurin	2.572	217456	3524	1.14
Mean			214378.8		
Std. Dev.			1791.516		
% RSD			0.835678		

3. Linearity & Range:

The calibration curve showed good linearity in the range of 6 – 14 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$, for Midostaurin (API) with correlation coefficient (r^2) of 0.999 (Fig-3). A typical calibration curve has the regression equation of $y = 19423x + 5444.4$ for Midostaurin [24].

Fig-3: Calibration Curve of Midostaurin (API)

Table-9: Linearity Results

CONC.(µg/ml)	MEAN AUC (n=6)
0ppm	0
6ppm	129013
8ppm	166523
10ppm	198315
12ppm	234151
14ppm	275819

Linearity Plot: The plot of Concentration (x) versus the Average Peak Area (y) data of Midostaurin is a straight line.

$$Y = mx + c$$

$$\text{Slope (m)} = 19423$$

$$\text{Intercept (c)} = 5444.4$$

$$\text{Correlation Coefficient (r)} = 0.99$$

Validation Criteria: The response linearity is verified if the Correlation Coefficient is 0.99 or greater.

Conclusion: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is 5444.4. These values meet the validation criteria [25].

4. Specificity:

The system suitability for specificity was carried out to determine whether there was any interference of any impurities in the retention time of the analytical peak.

Fig-4: Chromatogram for Blank Solution

Fig-5: Chromatogram of Midostaurin Standard Solution

Observation: The study was performed by injecting blank and standard into the system. There was no interference of any peak in the blank with the retention time of the analytical peaks [26].

5. Method Robustness: Influence of small changes in chromatographic conditions such as change in flow rate (± 0.1 ml/min), Wavelength of detection (± 2 nm) & organic phase in mobile phase ($\pm 5\%$) studied to determine the robustness of the method are also in favour of (Table-10, % RSD < 2%) the developed RP-HPLC method for the analysis of Midostaurin (API) [27].

Table-10: Results for Robustness for Midostaurin

Parameter Used for Sample Analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical Plates	Tailing Factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.0 mL/min	203654	2.570	2915	1.16
Less Flow rate of 0.9 mL/min	265876	2.573	3652	1.19
More Flow rate of 1.1 mL/min	298653	2.631	3854	1.20
Less Organic Phase	315874	2.590	3945	1.17
More Organic Phase	326985	2.602	3487	1.19

6. LOD & LOQ:

LOD: The detection limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be detected but not necessarily quantitated as an exact value [28].

$$\text{LOD} = 3.3 \times \sigma / s$$

Where

σ = Standard deviation of the response

S = Slope of the calibration curve

LOQ: The quantitation limit of an individual analytical procedure is the lowest amount of analyte in a sample which can be quantitatively determined [29].

$$\text{LOQ} = 10 \times \sigma / S$$

Where

σ = Standard deviation of the response

S = Slope of the calibration curve

Observation: The Minimum concentration level at which the analyte can be reliably detected (LOD) & quantified (LOQ) were found to be 0.08 & 0.24 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively.

7. System Suitability Parameter: System suitability was carried out with six injections of solution of 100% concentration having 10 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ of Avapritinib in to the chromatographic system [30]. Number of theoretical plates (N) obtained and calculated tailing factor (T) was reported in table-11.

Table-11: Data of System Suitability Parameter

S.No.	Parameter	Limit	Result
1	Asymmetry	$T \leq 2$	Midostaurin=0.23
2	Theoretical plate	$N > 2000$	Midostaurin=2987
3	Tailing Factor	$T < 2$	Midostaurin=1.17

8. Estimation of Midostaurin in Pharmaceutical Dosage Form

Twenty pharmaceutical dosage forms were taken and the I.P. strategy was taken after to decide the normal weight. Above measured tablets were at last powdered and triturated well. An amount of powder proportionate to 25 mg of medications were exchanged to 25 ml volumetric flagon, make and arrangement was sonicated for 15 minutes, there after volume was made up to 25 ml with same dissolvable. At that point 10 ml of the above arrangement was weakened to 100 ml with versatile stage. The arrangement was separated through a layer channel (0.45 μm) and sonicated to degas. The arrangement arranged was infused in five reproduces into the HPLC framework and the perceptions were recorded [31].

A copy infusion of the standard arrangement was additionally infused into the HPLC framework and the peak regions were recorded. The information is appeared in Table-12.

Assay % =

$$\frac{\text{AT}}{\text{AS}} \times \frac{\text{WS}}{\text{DS}} \times \frac{\text{DT}}{\text{WT}} \times \frac{\text{P}}{100} \times \text{Avg. Wt} = \text{mg/tab}$$

Where:

AT = Peak Area of medication acquired with test arrangement

AS = Peak Area of medication acquired with standard arrangement

WS = Weight of working standard taken in mg

WT = Weight of test taken in mg

DS = Dilution of Standard arrangement

DT = Dilution of test arrangement

P = Percentage virtue of working standard

Table-12: Recovery Data for estimation of Midostaurin in Alecensa 150mg Capsule

Brand Name of Midostaurin	Labelled amount of Drug (mg)	Mean (\pm SD) amount (mg) found by the proposed method (n=6)	Assay % (\pm SD)
Staurinz 25mg Capsule (Dr Reddy's Laboratories Ltd)	25mg	24.436 (\pm 0.385)	99.485 (\pm 0.359)

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

To develop a precise, linear, specific & suitable stability indicating RP-HPLC method for analysis of Midostaurin, different chromatographic conditions were applied & the results observed are presented in previous chapters. Isocratic elution is simple, requires only one pump & flat baseline separation for easy and reproducible results. So, it was preferred for the current study over gradient elution. In case of RP-HPLC various columns are available, but here Symmetry ODS (C₁₈) RP Column, 250 mm x 4.6 mm, 5 μm Column was preferred because using this column peak shape, resolution and absorbance were good. Discovery wavelength was chosen in the wake of examining the standard arrangement of medication more than 200 to 400nm. From the U.V range of Midostaurin it is apparent that a large portion of the HPLC works can be proficient in the wavelength scope of 210-300 nm helpfully. Further, a stream rate of 1.0 ml/min and an infusion volume of 10 μl were observed to be the best investigation. The outcome demonstrates the created technique is amazingly,

one more reasonable strategy for measure and dependability related debasement examines which can help in the investigation of Midostaurin in various details.

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